

What is your current education level?

Do you know what Citizen Science is?

Do you know what Open Science is?

Have you ever noticed concepts and/or practices of Citizen Science being used as part of your curriculum?

Do you think that Citizen Science could become part of your curriculum as:

What would you consider the most appropriate curriculum level for the course to be part of?

Were a Citizen Science project to take place during one of your classes, would you be interested in participating?

What are the skills that you would expect to take from participating in a Citizen Science course?

